

BENZYLTHIOUREAS. PART I

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Several mono- and N:N'-disubstituted benzylthioureas have been prepared for studying their biological properties.

Substituted thioureas show a wide variety of physiological activity, thus 4:4-dialkoxythiocarbaniilides show tuberculostatic properties (Huebner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2274) and are also active against human leprosy (Buu-Hoi, *Internat. J. Leprosy*, 1951, 22, 16). Certain diarylthioureas have been found active against influenza-virus infections in mice (Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1954, 238, 2582). Some arylthioureas have been reported to exhibit anthelmintic activity (Shimotani, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1952, 72, 328). Benzylthiourea shows antithyroid activity (Rascova, *Casopis Lékarů C'eskych*, 1947, 86, 979).

With a view to studying their physiological properties, several substituted benzylthioureas have been prepared from substituted benzylamines through the corresponding isothiocyanates, either by the action of ammonia or the appropriate amine.

Compounds 1 to 7 (Table I), when tested by the agar plate method, were found to show bacteriostatic activity against *Staphylococcus citreus*, *Staph. albus*, *Staph. aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and Typhus. Details will be published elsewhere.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Substituted benzylamines were prepared from the corresponding substituted benzyl halides by the method of Graymore (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1116).

Following the procedure described in "Organic Synthesis" (Vol. 21, p. 81) the substituted benzylamines were converted into the corresponding substituted benzyl isothiocyanates in yields varying from 50% to 70% (vide Table I).

TABLE I

Compounds. X=	B.P.	* D.	* Ref. index.	Formula.	Found.		Calc.	
					X%.	S%.	X%.	S%.
1. o-Cl	138°/6 mm.	1.203	1.5788	C ₈ H ₈ NCIS	19.3	17.4	19.3	17.5
2. m-Cl	140°-45°/6	1.201	1.5784	" "	19.3	17.4	" "	" "
3. p-Cl	130-33°/4	1.206	1.5698	" "	19.2	17.4	" "	" "
4. o-Br	130-34°/5	1.403	1.6048	C ₈ H ₈ NBrS	35.0	14.0	35.0	14.1
5. m-Br	147°/5	1.501	1.6384	" "	35.0	14.0	" "	" "
6. p-Br	140-44°/5-7	1.381	1.6037	" "	34.9	13.9	" "	" "
7. p-I	167°/3-4	1.521	1.6088	C ₈ H ₈ NIS	46.1	11.7	46.1	11.6
8. m-I	162°/3-4	1.667	1.6170	" "	46.0	11.6	" "	" "

* Density and refractive index (sodium light) were determined at 27°.

Following the same method as above, mono-substituted thioureas were prepared in quantitative yields by the action of ammonia on substituted benzyl isothiocyanates. N:N'-disubstituted thioureas were prepared in quantitative yields by the action of

primary amines on the substituted benzyl isothiocyanates using the method of Kaye and Parris (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1862). Mono- and N,N'-disubstituted thioureas prepared are shown in Tables II and III respectively. Thioureas crystallised from hot water or alcohol usually in needles.

TABLE II
X-C₆H₄CH₂-NHCSNH₂.

Substance. X =	M.P.	Formula.	Found.		Calc.	
			X%	S%	X%	S%
1. <i>o</i> -Cl	126°	C ₈ H ₉ N ₂ ClS	17.6	16.0	17.7	15.9
2. <i>m</i> -Cl	133°	" "	17.6	15.9	" "	" "
3. <i>p</i> -Cl	141°	" "	17.6	15.9	" "	" "
4. <i>o</i> -Br	127°	C ₈ H ₉ N ₂ BrS	32.6	13.0	32.6	13.1
5. <i>m</i> -Br	151°	" "	32.6	13.1	" "	" "
6. <i>p</i> -Br	157°	" "	32.5	13.1	" "	" "
7. <i>p</i> -I	162-64°	C ₈ H ₉ N ₂ IS	43.4	11.0	43.4	10.9
8. <i>m</i> -I	151°	" "	43.4	10.9	" "	" "

TABLE III
X-C₆H₄CH₂-NHCSNH-R.

Substance. X =	R =	M.P.	Formula.	Found.		Calc.		
				X%	S%	X%	S%	
9.	<i>o</i> -Cl	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	165°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ ClS	12.2	11.0	12.2	11.0
10.	<i>m</i> -Cl	" "	84°	" "	12.2	11.1	" "	" "
11.	<i>p</i> -Cl	" "	140°	" "	13.2	11.0	" "	" "
12.	<i>o</i> -Br	" "	102°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ BrS	23.8	9.5	23.8	9.6
13.	<i>m</i> -Br	" "	90°	" "	23.8	9.5	" "	" "
14.	<i>p</i> -Br	" "	139°	" "	23.8	9.6	" "	" "
15.	<i>p</i> -I	" "	103°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ IS	33.2	8.4	33.2	8.4
16.	<i>o</i> -Cl	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	157°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ ClS	10.8	9.8	10.9	9.8
17.	<i>m</i> -Cl	" "	124°	" "	10.8	9.8	" "	" "
18.	<i>p</i> -Cl	" "	143°	" "	10.8	9.8	" "	" "
19.	<i>o</i> -Br	" "	163°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ BrS	21.5	8.6	21.5	8.6
20.	<i>m</i> -Br	" "	149°	" "	21.5	8.7	" "	" "
21.	<i>p</i> -Br	" "	157°	" "	21.5	8.6	" "	" "
22.	<i>p</i> -I	" "	166°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ IS	30.3	7.6	30.3	7.7
23.	<i>m</i> -I	" "	156°	" "	30.3	7.6	" "	" "
24.	<i>o</i> -Cl	β -C ₁₀ H ₇	160°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ ClS	10.8	9.8	10.9	9.8
25.	<i>m</i> -Cl	" "	153°	" "	10.8	9.8	" "	" "
26.	<i>p</i> -Cl	" "	169°	" "	10.8	9.7	" "	" "
27.	<i>o</i> -Br	" "	161°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ BrS	21.5	8.6	21.5	8.6
28.	<i>m</i> -Br	" "	163°	" "	21.5	8.6	21.5	8.6
29.	<i>p</i> -Br	" "	173°	" "	21.5	8.6	" "	" "
30.	<i>p</i> -I	" "	180°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ IS	30.3	7.6	30.3	7.7
31.	<i>m</i> -I	" "	172°	" "	30.2	7.6	" "	" "

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